

Can E-Learning Replace Classroom Learning

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ABSTRACT

Learning is acquiring knowledge or skills through study, experience, or being taught. Various innovations in Information and Technology have changed the way of learning as well. E-learning is the learning conducted through electronic media. The emergence of COVID-19 as a global pandemic has led to the growth of e-learning as a global platform for learning. The pandemic has compelled the use of e-learning in education. In this regard, an attempt has been made to identify the pros and cons of e-learning, to identify problems faced by students in e-learning and to suggest certain measures to make e-learning as an effective tool. For the purpose of study, google form is used to collect the information. The data is collected from 104 respondents studying in different colleges.

Keywords: E-learning, Classroom learning, ICT

1. INTRODUCTION:

E-learning also existed even before 1980s in the form of distance learning and television courses. But with the growth of Information Communication & Technology, its area got widened. The increased usage of Internet, Social media and smart phones facilitated people to easily access information, discuss in online platforms, clarify their queries, broaden their knowledge, etc. Evolution of different online certificate courses, YouTube videos, online tutorials has increased the importance of e-learning. We are no longer confined to physical libraries to gain deeper knowledge, no longer confined to search a topic in a book, no longer confined to classrooms to complete a course. All these could be done through virtual aids. E-learning facilitates transmission of information in the form of videos, pictures, slides, documents, or PDFs through the use of internet. Now students can communicate with the professors or experts through various social networking tools. Distance is no longer a barrier in learning.

Earlier, e-learning was not accepted whole heartedly in education sector as it lacks personal interaction in learning. But the emergence of COVID-19 pandemic has compelled the use of e-learning in education sector. Though it was a big challenge, Schools and colleges chose various e-learning methods to teach the students, instead of wasting the academic year. Various software programs were developed to aid e-learning. Various conferences, workshops, webinars were organized to train the use of e-learning resources in education sector. Teachers learnt the use of modern methods in teaching. COVID 2nd wave gave no other option than to continue learning online.

E-Learning:

E-learning is the learning conducted through electronic resources. It is also called as electronic learning, internet learning, computerized learning, online learning. It is a network enabled

acquiring of knowledge, information and skills. It includes the use of computers, smart phones, electronic devices and internet. Under this, lectures can be delivered live online or through recorded videos or audios. They are popular in certain certificate courses, certain tutorial apps and now they are widely being used in the education sector also.

Pros of E-Learning:

1. E-learning is flexible as learning can be done at the convenience of the learner.
2. E-learning helps in covering the distance between the learner and teacher. There is no geographical limitation in learning.
3. It is cost effective since it reduces the cost of the learner as he/she need not physically move to the source of education.
4. Recordings of the sessions helps the learner to replay the same for any clarifications.
5. It is especially helpful during this COVID pandemic and lockdown where classroom teaching is impossible to conduct.

Cons of E-Learning:

1. It lacks strong bonding between the teacher and the learner
2. It needs to have proper internet connection and devices to enable e-learning
3. Difficult to use in case of practical learning
4. Health related issues like stress, headache, eye strain, back pain etc.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To study the perception of graduate and postgraduate students towards e-learning compared to classroom learning.
- To study the problems faced by them in e-learning.
- To suggest certain measures to utilise e- learning based on the findings.

3. METHODOLOGY:

Primary and secondary data are used for study. An online questionnaire is used to collect the information from 104 respondents. Non-probability sampling technique is used for data collection. Secondary data is collected from journals, articles and related websites.

4. LIMITATIONS:

- The sample size is comparatively smaller.
- Primary data has its own limitations which might affect the conclusion of the study.
- The study simply presents the findings and has not used other advanced statistical methods.

5. DATA ANALYSIS:

Only simple statistical tool and the percentage analysis are used for the analysis and interpretation of the data.

Table 1: Personal details of respondents:

Particulars	Count	Percentage
Total	104	100%
A. Gender		
Male	26	25.00%
Female	78	75.00%
B. Degree		
Graduate	82	78.85%
Post-graduate	22	21.15%
C. Year of Studying		
I Year	43	41.35%
II Year	39	37.50%
III Year	19	18.27%
IV Year	03	02.88%
D. Institution		
Govt Institute	77	74.04%
Private Institute	27	25.96%

Table 1 shows that there were 104 respondents, consisting 26 male and 78 female and majority (78.85%) are doing their graduation. Most of the respondents are studying in their first year. Majority respondents are from government colleges.

Table 2: Mode of Communication used in e-learning by teachers to communicate with the students

	Count	%
Emails	11	9.57
Whatsapp	75	65.22
Forums	06	5.22

Chats	21	18.26
Blogs	0	0.00
Others	2	1.74

Table 2 shows that majority teachers use whatsapp application in e-learning to communicate information to the students.

Table 3: The devices used by the students for study in e-learning

	Count	%
Computer	06	5.77
Laptop	08	7.69
Smart Phone	90	86.54

Table 3 shows that majority students i.e.,86.54% use smart phones in their e-learning process.

Table 4: Preference of the place for the use of internet in e-learning:

Particulars	Count	%
At Home	85	81.73%
At the University	18	17.31%
At an Internet Café	01	00.96%

Table 4 shows that majority of the students prefer to use internet for e-learning at their home.

Table 5: Do you enjoy learning through e-learning?

	Count	%
Yes	40	38.46%
No	40	38.46%
Can't Say	24	23.08%

Table 5 shows that 38.46 % respondents enjoy e-learning, again 38.46% don't enjoy e-learning and 23.08% are neutral regarding the same.

Table 6: Do you think e-learning is a waste of time?

	Count	%
Yes	24	23.08

No	55	52.88
Neutral	25	24.04

Figure 1 (Table 6) shows that majority of the respondents do not think that e-learning is a waste of time.

Table 7: Do you think e-learning is better than classroom learning?

	Count	%
Yes	19	18.27%
No	85	81.73%

Figure 2 (Table 7) shows that majority of the respondents do not think that e-learning is better than classroom learning.

Table 8: Do you think e-learning can replace classroom learning?

	Count	%
Yes	19	18.45%
No	61	59.22%
Neutral	24	23.07%

Figure 3(Table 8) shows that majority of the respondents do not think that e-learning can replace classroom learning.

Table 9: Do you think for practical classes, classroom learning is better than e-learning?

	Count	%
Yes	65	63.11%
No	29	28.16%
Neutral	10	9.61%

Figure 4 (Table 9) shows that majority of the respondents think that for practical classes classroom learning is better than e-learning.

Table 10: Students perception of Advantages of e-learning:

	Count	%
It is more convenient than classroom learning	05	2.63%
It is more effective than classroom learning	03	1.58%
It helps to study at anytime	72	37.89%
It helps to study at any place	51	26.84%
It saves time and cost	30	15.79%
It is interesting and useful	8	4.21%
It is helpful in developing knowledge	17	8.95%

Figure 5 (Table 10) shows that majority of the respondents felt that E-learning is helpful as it helps to study at any time, at any place and also it saves time & cost

Table 11: Difficulties faced by them in E-learning

	Count	%
Lacks personal touch	59	22.52
Difficult to clarify doubts	52	19.85
Difficult to handle	23	8.78
Technical problems	29	11.07
Internet problems	57	21.76
Prefer to learn through books	30	11.45
Unavailability of proper devices	10	3.82
Harmful to health	4	0.76

Figure 6(Table 11) shows that majority of the respondents face difficulties like no personal touch as in classroom learning, Internet problems, difficulty in clarifying doubts in e-learning.

Table 12: Do you think classroom learning along with e-learning can be an effective method?

	Count	%
Yes	75	72.82%
No	27	26.21%
Neutral	2	0.97%

Figure 7 (Table 12) shows that majority of the respondents think that classroom learning along with e-learning can be an effective method.

6. FINDINGS:

1. Some opined that it acts as an alternate solution for classroom teaching during COVID-19 Pandemic period.

2. Through e-learning they got the chance of learning new concepts and access to new types of learning.
3. Through the PPTs, they could understand the concepts in a better way rather than having only books and blackboards.
4. They opined that it is useful for people who cannot attend the classes.
5. Some of the respondents found it difficult to understand certain concepts through e-learning. They also opined that clarification of doubts and queries is difficult in e-learning.
6. Their major issue was with regard to Internet problem and health issues.
7. Some of the respondents opined that they lack the bond between teacher & student in e-learning which was strong in class room learning.
8. They also found that they had positive environment of learning in classroom which is absent in e-learning. They face lack of concentration in e-learning.
9. They opined that in classroom learning, they can clarify their doubts not only through their teachers but also through their classmates.

7. SUGGESTIONS:

1. There is a need of supportive environment for the exchange of ideas and information between the teachers and the students.
2. Group study and discussion could be encouraged through interactive online classes.
3. Proper training of the various e-learning resources would be beneficial for the teachers to use them effectively and to make their teaching effective.
4. Flipped classrooms could be used to have more involvement of students.
5. Teachers could utilise various e-resources to enhance their presentations.
6. E-learning requires the learner to be self-disciplined, self-driven and have positive approach towards learning.

8. CONCLUSION:

E-learning and classroom learning cannot be replaced with one another. Both the methods have their own benefits and limitations. Both are helpful in increasing the knowledge and skills of the learner. Class room learning helps in creating good study environments, discipline, personal interactions and also allows teachers to know, encourage and evaluate their students. E-learning helps in using modern methods to make the concepts clearer, more understandable and access to updated information. Blending of both the methodologies in a proper way is needed to enhance learning. A supportive environment, interactive classes, proper training to faculties, proper resources, positive approach towards e-learning are needed for the success of e-learning.

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